

Key Challenges and Opportunities for Expanding Source-Separating Sanitation System in the EU

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1. Abstract

Source-separating sanitation systems (SSSS) involve the separate collection and treatment of distinct wastewater fractions, enabling the recycling of nutrients, e.g., nitrogen and phosphorus from urban wastewater and human excreta as valuable resources. Although, existing research has explored the potential of SSSS, there remains a gap in understanding the relative importance of specific barriers and opportunities from a multi-stakeholder perspective across the European Union. This study addresses this gap by categorizing and ranking challenges and opportunities using the PESTEL framework. Data was collected through a survey of Quadruple Helix stakeholders (n=55) across 15 EU countries, who assessed the intensity of each factor using a 10-point scale. The Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) was then applied to derive weighted rankings based on stakeholder judgments. The key challenges include the presence of pathogens and pollutants, seasonal environmental impacts, and vulnerability to environmental disasters, reflecting strong environmental concerns. Institutional issues such as an inconsistent regulatory framework and political resistance and rigidities also emerged as key barriers. Conversely, the top-ranked opportunities include stricter pollution and climate regulations, legislative support for nutrient reuse, and reduced dependence on phosphorus and fossil-based fertilizers. Additional enablers such as enhanced municipal-utility cooperation and improved nutrient recycling signal the importance of systemic coordination and environmental incentives. These findings provide targeted insights for policy and practice, highlighting priority areas for intervention. Addressing regulatory fragmentation, environmental risks, and institutional inertia while strengthening legislative frameworks and inter-organizational coordination will be essential for advancing the implementation and scalability of SSSS across the EU.

1.1 Research questions

- RQ1: What are the key challenges and opportunities for expanding SSSS in the EU?
- RQ2: How do different stakeholder groups perceive these challenges and opportunities?
- RQ3: What policy recommendations can be developed to support the expansion of SSSS?

2. Methodology

Stage 1:

- **PESTEL framework** was applied to classify 25 **challenges** and 25 **opportunities** across Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal dimensions (Tsangas et al., 2019).
- **Quadruple Helix model (QH)** was used to group stakeholders into Academia, Industry, Government, and Civil Society (Cai & Lattu, 2022).

Stage 2:

- **Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)** was employed to structure challenges/opportunities hierarchically and prioritize them based on expert input (Figures 1 & 2). **Pairwise comparison survey** was designed tailored to each QH stakeholder group. Participants rated the **relative importance** of each PESTEL indicator on a 10-point scale (10=highest priority) (Saaty, 1980; Forman & Gass, 2001).

3. Results

3.1 Categorization of opportunities and challenges indicators using the PESTEL Framework

Fig. 1. Hierarchical tree of opportunities for expanding SSSS

Fig. 2. Hierarchical tree of challenges for expanding SSSS

3.2 Data Collection

- Survey period: Dec 6, 2024 – Mar 1, 2025
- Total responses: **94**
- Final dataset: **55 valid responses**
- Geographical: **15 European countries**

Fig. 3. Country representation in the survey, % of total participants

3.3 Overall priority weights for challenges and opportunities indicators (Germany, Spain and Sweden)

Fig. 4, 5 & 6. Overall challenges ranking: Germany (4), Spain (5) & Sweden (6)

3.4 Quadruple helix stakeholder perspective on key challenges and opportunities for expanding SSSS

Fig. 10. Challenges indicators ranking: QH stakeholders' perspective

Fig. 11. Opportunities indicators ranking: QH stakeholders' perspective

4. Discussion and conclusions

The findings reveal both **convergence and divergence in stakeholder views**, offering critical insights into areas of alignment and friction. Several highly ranked opportunities, such as **stricter pollution regulations** and **municipal-utility cooperation**, correspond closely with top-ranked challenges like **regulatory inconsistency** and **political resistance**. This overlap underscores the need for a comprehensive policy mix, combining:

- **Cross-sectoral stakeholder collaboration**
- **Adaptive governance mechanisms**
- **Socially grounded innovation pathways**

Importantly, the results emphasize that the successful scaling of SSSS requires a coordinated, multi-stakeholder approach. Strategic investments and policy interventions should be guided by the most salient priorities shared across groups, while remaining sensitive to specific sectoral concerns.

References:

Cai, Y., & Lattu, M. (2022). The Quadruple Helix model and innovation policy in the European Union. *Journal of Innovation and Knowledge*, 7(1), 100–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2022.01.001>
 Forman, E. H., & Gass, S. I. (2001). The Analytic Hierarchy Process—An exposition. *Operations Research*, 49(4), 469–486. <https://doi.org/10.1287/opre.49.4.469.11231>
 Saaty, T. L. (1980). *The Analytic Hierarchy Process: Planning, priority setting, resource allocation*. McGraw-Hill.
 Tsangas, G., Giannopoulou, M., Panori, A., & Kakderi, C. (2019). A PESTEL-based framework for addressing urban sustainability. *Sustainability*, 11(20), 5757. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11205757>